

THE PREVALENCE OF DRY EYE DISEASE AMONG PROFESSIONAL COMPUTER USERS

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Abstract

Introduction: Dry eye disease is developed due to deformities in the tear film that comprises of lipid, aqueous & mucous layers from anterior to posterior side. Dry eye disease is considered amongst one of the most predominant conditions observed in the ophthalmology outdoor setting. Because of the instability in tear film, patients suffering with this disease may present with various degree of redness, irritation, watering, burning, grittiness, foreign body sensation and transient blurring of vision. The signs of dry eye disease may even be present in the absence of full harmony of these above mentioned characteristics.

Objective: To determine the frequency of dry eyes disease among the professional computer users.

Study Design: Cross sectional study.

Place: Department of Ophthalmology, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.

Study period: Present research was conducted from 04-08-2017 to 03-02-2018.

Material and Methods: This cross sectional study was conducted at Jinnah Hospital Lahore. Informed written consent was taken. Complete ophthalmic examination including detailed anterior segment examination on slit lamp was performed. Then, tear film break time (TBUT) was measured using 2% fluorescein dye drops, which were instilled in the inferior conjunctival sac / fornix. The patients were asked to blink several times for equal distribution of dye in entire tear film and then were asked to keep the eyes open and do not blink any further while the tear film was being observed under the cobalt blue broad beam illumination on slit lamp. The TBUT was the interval, recorded in seconds, for the appearance of 1st black spot or line in the fluorescein-stained tear film, indicating the formation of dry areas. A TBUT of less than 10 seconds is taken as abnormal.

Results: The mean age of patients was 40.82 ± 9.92 years. The minimum duration of working on computers was 5 years and maximum was 16 years with mean and standard deviation 9.34 ± 3.32 years. There were 64.4% male computer user while female computer users were 35.6%. There were 54.8% smokers while 45.2% were non smokers. There were 60% cases who uses computer in air conditioned rooms while 40% computer users without air conditioned rooms. Dry eye disease was present in 18.5% professional computer users while dry eye disease was not present in 81.5% computer users.

Conclusion: Dry eye disease was present in 18.5% among the professional computer users. Effect modifiers have no significant influence on the presence of dry eye disease.

Key words: Dry Eye Disease, Professional Computer Users, Tear Film Break Up Time, Prevalence.

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Dry eye disease is the multi-factorial disease of ocular surface which occurs due to the presence of optical distress. It is also called as keratoconjunctivitis sicca or dysfunctional tear disorder.¹ The precise incidence of dry eye disease is not well known because of the trouble in the definition of the disease and the shortage of single appropriate diagnostic tool to confirm the presence of dry eyes disease. But, the incidence of dry eye disease rises with increasing age and is projected to be presence in 5 – 30% of people aged 50 years or above. This incidence is estimated to rise as the people living in the developed countries continues to age.^{2,3}

Sjögren's syndrome is the long-lasting provocative disease featured by reduced functioning of lacrimal & salivary glands. Risk factors specific for Sjögren's Syndrome include a genetic predisposition, low androgen status, nutritional deficiencies, and exposure to environmental agents.⁴ The problem of dry eye can significantly affect the visual acuity of individual, daily routine, social & physical health as well as workplace efficiency.⁵ In addition, patients with dry eye incur direct medical costs through frequent visits to health care professionals, as well as pharmacologic and non-pharmacologic therapies. Indirect costs include decreased productivity and time lost from work.⁶ A cost analysis study estimates an overall annual cost of \$55.4 billion to the United States from a societal perspective.⁷

Dry eye disease is the complex and multi-factorial complication. The tear film of eyes consists of lipid components, aqueous & mucous layers. The healthy tear film depends on the synergistic interface of the eyelids, lacrimal glands & ocular surfaces, which collectively compose a lacrimal functional unit. Dysfunction in any component of lacrimal functional unit may cause the development of dry eye disease.⁸ The use of personal computers, laptops or mobile / tablets in recent decade, has been increased extensively and the drastic rise in the work load and duration of using visual display terminals. The number of people using these visual display terminals is increasing all over the world with increasing

use of Internet. During year 2012, the frequency of Internet users all over the world was reported as 2.4 billion, which was doubled rate as estimated in previous 5 years.⁹ In Japan during 2010, about 95 million individuals (80% of population) were using the visual display terminals with Internet.¹⁰

Lengthy working on the visual display terminals is found to be associated with general and musculo-skeletal symptoms like physical tiredness, back ache and also pain in shoulders & wrists.¹¹ Additionally, work on visual display terminals has been found to be associated with ocular symptoms including loss of visual acuity, asthenopia, pain in eyes and dry eyes disease due to increase rate of tear vaporization, reduced blinking rate, and less tear emission.¹² In few epidemiological surveys, by using the questionnaire, prolonged use of visual display terminals was significantly associated with pattern concerning the higher prevalence of symptoms of dry eye and clinically diagnosed as the dry eye disease. The pathogenesis of dry eye disease symptoms among users of visual display terminals might be because of alterations in the configuration of the tear films.¹³

During the last decade, computer and laptop use have turned to an integral part of modern life. It is projected that, since 2000, around 75% of all the jobs in routine activities, computer use is necessary.¹⁴ Owing to the high capacity and increase trend in computer use, several studies tried to evaluate the way for protection of eyes and the several researches involved in these studies are distributed to determine the effects of the computers and visual display terminal. In starting, these studies were focused mostly to determine the radiation and its harmful effects, but progressively ophthalmic illnesses because of the exposure to the video display terminals turn out to be the major focus and the terminology “computer vision syndrome” was developed to refer to such illnesses. Among these illnesses as reported by user of video display, the problem of red eye, blurry vision, diplopia, burning & irritation, as well as weakness of eye are most common.¹⁵

METHODOLOGY

This cross sectional survey was done at Department of Ophthalmology, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore. The study was conducted for 6 months i.e. from August 04, 2017 to February 03, 2017. In the study, sample size of n=135 cases was estimated by keeping 95% confidence interval, 6% margin of error and percentage of dry eye disease as 14.6%. All the patients were included by applying Non-probability, consecutive sampling technique. Person from both genders with age 25-60 years of age, using computer in their profession with best corrected visual acuity of 6/6 measured by Snellen's Visual acuity chart were included. The person who uses computer for at least 5 hours a day and 5 days a week for last six months was labeled as a professional computer user were included in the study. On examination if person has any one of the following findings, he/she was excluded from the study: previous intraocular surgeries including Extra Capsular Cataract Extraction, Phacoemulsification, Iridectomy, patients having any pathology of eyelids i.e. chalazion or blepharitis, corneal ulcer, scleritis, allergic conjunctivitis, basal cell carcinoma or Squamous cell carcinoma or with best corrected visual acuity of worse than 6/6 so to avoid any confounding factors of asthenopia that may be occurring due to the uncorrected refractive error. Sociodemographic data like name, age, sex was documented. A pre-designed proforma was filled by the investigator himself in language of the participant. Then, complete ophthalmic examination was performed including detailed anterior segment examination with slit lamp. Then, tear film break time (TBUT) was assessed by using 2% fluorescein dye solution. To assess the TBUT of the patients, fluorescein was implanted in the tear film of the patients and patients were requested to keep eye open and do not blink for few seconds, meanwhile the tear film was observed under the broad beam of cobalt blue illumination. The TBUT was noted the time lapse, in terms of seconds, between two blinks and the presence of 1st dry spot in tear film. Dry eye disease was charac-

terized by using the TBUT and the patient with tear film break time of less than 10 seconds was labeled as having dry eye disease.

Data Analysis: The data was analyzed by using SPSS v. 20.0. Numeric variables such as age & duration of using computers was presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation. Categorical variables such as sex & smoking were presented as frequency and percentages

RESULTS

From 135 cases, it was observed that the minimum age was 25 years and maximum age was 60 years with mean and standard deviation of the age was 40.82 ± 9.92 years. The minimum duration of working was 5 years and maximum was 16 years with mean and standard deviation 9.34 ± 3.32 years.

There were 87/135 (64.4%) male computer user while female computer users were 48/135 (35.6%). There were 74/135 (54.8%) smokers while 61/135 (45.2%) were not smokers. There were 81/135 (60%) cases who uses computer in air conditioned rooms while 54/135 (40%) computer users without air conditioned rooms. Dry eye disease was present in 25/135 (18.5%) professional computer users while dry eye disease was not present in 110/135 (81.5%) computer users.

By using chi-square test, there was no significant association between dry eye disease and gender having p-value = 0.181. Significant association was not found between stratified age group and dry eye disease with p-value 0.069. Significant association was not found between duration of professional computer use and dry eye disease with p-value 0.591. Significant association was not found between the availability of air-conditioned room and Dry Eye Disease with p-value 0.366. There was no significant association between dry eye disease and smokers having p-value = 0.307.

Table 1: Characteristics of candidates

N	135
Age	40.82 ± 9.92
Gender	
Male	87 (64.4%)
Female	48 (35.6%)
Duration of using computer	9.34 ± 3.32
Smoking	
Yes	74 (54.8%)
No	61 (45.2%)
Air conditioned room	
Yes	81 (60%)
No	54 (40%)

Fig 1: Distribution of Dry Eye Disease

DISCUSSION

In our study the mean age of the patients was 40.82 ± 9.92 years. The minimum duration was 5

Table 2: Stratification with Respect to Effect Modifiers

		Dry Eye Disease		Total	P - value
		Present	Absent		
Gender	Male	19	68	87	0.181
	Female	6	42	48	
Age (years)	< 43 years	10	66	76	0.069
	≥ 43 years	15	44	59	
Duration of professional computer use	< 10 years	14	68	82	0.591
	≥ 10 years	11	42	53	
Availability of Air-conditioned room	Yes	17	64	81	0.366
	No	8	46	54	
Smokers	Yes	16	58	74	0.307
	No	9	52	61	

years and maximum was 16 years with mean and standard deviation 9.34 ± 3.32 years. There were 64.4% male computer user while female computer

users were 35.6%. There were 54.8% smokers while 45.2% were not smokers. There were 60% cases who uses computer in air conditioned rooms while 40% computer users without air conditioned rooms. Dry eye disease was observed in 18.5% professional computer users while dry eye disease was absent in 81.5% computer users.

In previous study, out of 9049 detected studies, 16 were included, with total of 11,365 workers of visual display terminals. Regardless of the high frequency of dry eye disease (49.5%, 95% CI; 47.5 to 50.6), ranged from 9.5% to 87.5%, significant heterogeneity (I2 = 98.8%, p < 0.0001) was detected. Few studies joined the criteria to define dry eye disease. Heterogeneous prevalence was related to the stratifications on symptoms (I2 = 98.7%, p < 0.0001), tears (I2 = 98.5%, p < 0.0001) and epithelial injury (I2 = 96.0%, p < 0.0001). The prevalence of dry eye disease was reported to be more common in women as compared to the men and also more common in older age individuals than younger ones. Because of the differences in the diagnostic method considered to define dry eye disease, the prevalence of dry eye disease all over the world was considered to be 49.5% has less consistency owing to very significant heterogeneity.¹⁶

Present literature displayed that the crude rate of dry eye disease was observed as 30.3%, while the age-, gender-, & region - adjusted rate was 33.2%. Females (P = 0.01) and urban inhabitants (P = 0.001) were more prone to develop the dry eye disease. Individuals having dry eye disease, 85.1% displayed the TBUT time less than or equal to 10 sec, 54.1% were diagnosed with dysfunction of meibomian gland, 39.2% attained the fluorescein score of 1 or greater, while 32.8% cases attained the Schirmer test score of less than or equal to 5 mm. The low Schirmer score was significantly associated with high prevalence of dry eye disease, though the sensitivity was less. Dry eye disease was significantly more correlated with older age; female gender and inhabitants living in the urban regions.¹⁷

In another study, conducted by Schaumberg et al., it was reported that the rate of dry eye disease

rises with the increasing age, i.e. from 5.7% in females aged < 50 years to 9.8% in females of age above 75 years or more. In United States, the age - adjusted prevalence of dry eye syndrome was 7.8%, or 3.23 million of females of age 50 years of above. Compared to the Whites, the females of Hispanics (odds ratio = 1.81, 95% CI; 1.18 -2.80) & Asian (odds ratio = 1.77, 95% CI; 1.17 - 2.69) region were more prone to report the severe signs, but are not clinically diagnosed for dry eye syndrome. The difference was insignificant for income (P - value = 0.78), but females who have more qualification had less chances of developing dry eye disease (P=0.03) than uneducated or less educated females. Females of the Southern countries have the highest rate of dry eye disease, however the extent of topographical differences was uncertain.¹⁸

CONCLUSION

Dry eye disease was present in 18.5% among the professional computer users. Effect modifiers have no significant influence on the presence of dry eye disease.

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